

Statistical Similarities and Differences between the Maxwell-Boltzmann Factor and $\exp(ipx)$

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e/T)$ and the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ have a similar form in that they are both exponentials. This has the important feature that a product $\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-e_3/T)\exp(-e_4/T)$ if $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$ (i.e. local conservation of energy) and $\exp(ip_1 \cdot r) \exp(ip_2 \cdot r) = \exp(ip_3 \cdot r)\exp(ip_4 \cdot r)$ if $p_1 + p_2 = p_3+p_4$ (vectors) i.e. local conservation of momentum.

There is, however, a fundamental difference in that $\exp(-e/T)$ contains a global parameter T related to the global sum of all e values, while $\exp(ipx)$ contains no such global parameter. In the case of momentum being a vector, the sum of various vectors could be the 0 vector or take on any value so one is not distributing a positive quantity as in the case of energy. As a result, $\exp(ipx)$ functions on the local level and describes conservation of momentum. To link $\exp(ipx)$ with a distributed quantity and positive real probabilities, one must associate it with $P(p,x)dx = dx/L$. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamic kind of square root probability in terms of quantity distribution. For example, for a single particle quantum bound state, one creates a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. This may be used to calculate average kinetic energy at x , yet $W^*(x)W(x)$ is the motion frozen spatial density (like a distribution density) as is $a^*(p)a(p)$ which shows how E_n , the bound state energy is distributed into p values.

We have argued in previous notes that $\exp(-e/T)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ are both solutions of local extremization of Shannon's entropy procedures, but the MB case involves a Lagrange multiplier linked with global energy, while $\exp(ipx)$ does not. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ represents a dynamic probability lurking under the usual distributed probability $P(x,p)$, and that the two are linked by freezing out motion, i.e. $P(x,p) = \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)/L$, then using this freeze recipe for different p values and integrating over x leads to 0. This has important consequences because it means that $\exp(ipx)$ s are orthogonal.

For a bound state with a potential $V(x)$ and total energy E , one knows the classical (average) kinetic energy at x . This means one does not use the extremization of entropy to find the weights $a(p)$, because orthogonality seems to guarantee a unique solution for $a(p)$ s for a specific E_n . In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ follows from extremization of Shannon's entropy with no global considerations of a p total for many particles, and even taking an average of $\exp(ipx)$ s and using it in a conservation of energy constraint leads to a unique solution of weights when using conservation of average energy as the resulting differential equation has unique solutions for each E_n if one uses appropriate boundary conditions. One may note that this whole process occurs at the level of the wavefunction, where there is no globally distributed quantity, while $\exp(-e/T)$ exists at the level of a distributed quantity, namely total energy.

The Notion of Distributed Quantity

In the classical world, one often deals with the distribution of a quantity such that one has a sum of positive values adding to a total. It is possible to assign positive probabilities to these values such that the sum of probabilities adds to 1. For a Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one adds single particle energies to obtain a total energy. If there is a probability associated with each e_i , then

$$E_{ave} = \sum_i P(e_i)e_i \quad ((1))$$

We argue that one may apply a similar distribution to a bound classical particle. In this case, there exists a probability for the particle to be at a particular x point and one may calculate an $X_{ave} = \sum_i P(x_i)x_i$, like in the case of energy.

$$P(x)dx = Cdt = Cdx/v \text{ or for a constant } v \text{ and } p, \quad P(x)dx = dx/L \text{ where } L \text{ is length} \quad ((2))$$

This is well-known in the literature.

The point we wish to make is that $P(x)$ is on the same footing as $P(e)$, i.e. is associated with positive real probabilities. The problem that exists, as pointed out in (1), is that $P(x)dx$ applies to all p values and so is equivalent to a static distribution. If one considers motion, one would like a p,x based probability $P_{\text{special}}(x,p)$, i.e. a dynamic probability. We suggested in (1) that this probability follows from freezing out motion by using an AND situation i.e.

$$P(x,p)dx = dx/L = P_{\text{special}}(x,-p)P_{\text{special}}(x,p) \quad ((3))$$

This leads to a solution of $P_{\text{special}} = \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ if one wants the solution to be periodic. Formally, however, $\exp(ipx)$ may be obtained from the maximization of Shannon's entropy, as we have argued in previous notes, by using $ipx P_{\text{special}}$ as a constraint i.e.

$$\text{Extremize } P_{\text{special}} \ln(P_{\text{special}}) + ipx P_{\text{special}} \quad ((4))$$

A Comparison of $\exp(-e/T)$ and $\exp(ipx)$

As a result, the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e/T)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ have a similar functional form. The similarity, however, goes far beyond this, we argue. This form is exactly what is required for AND products to be the same for a fixed e_1+e_2 or p_1+p_2 , i.e. all bias has been removed which seems to be an important idea behind the maximization of entropy. Furthermore, this removal of bias and equity of AND probabilities is associated with local conservation.

In the case of $\exp(-e/T)$:

$$\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-e_3/T)\exp(-e_4/T) \quad \text{where } e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4 \quad ((5A))$$

In the case of $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(ip \cdot r)$:

$$\exp(ip_1 \cdot r)\exp(ip_2 \cdot r) = \exp(ip_3 \cdot r)\exp(ip_4 \cdot r) \quad \text{where } p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4 \text{ vector} \quad ((5B))$$

In other words, in one case one has a conservation of energy expression while in the other a conservation of momentum. Each of these conservation laws may exist at a local level, i.e. pertain to a single collision of two particles, without any considerations of the global environment. Given that energy is a distributed quantity, however, the local conservation law may be combined with a global scenario, i.e. $\exp(-e/T)$ may be proportional to the number of particles in a global situation with energy e and T may be a global parameter associated with global average energy.

In the case of momentum, one does not usually think in terms of an overall distribution of a quantity because it is a vector. The bigger issue, however, is that $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamic probability which exists to describe interactions. Thus it must be associated with local conservation of momentum. The difference with $\exp(-e/T)$ is that the distributed quantity is associated with $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$, i.e. the static probability. Global features exist at this level, while local exist at the $\exp(ipx)$ level. This seems to be a fundamental difference between classical statistical mechanics and quantum.

As a result, $\exp(-e/T)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ both follow from extremization of Shannon's entropy to remove bias, which is equivalent to a local conservation law, but $\exp(-e/T)$ is linked with a distributed quantity, while $\exp(ipx)$ is only linked with interactions and its corresponding distributed quantity exists a different level, i.e. the motion frozen $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$. We have touched on some of these ideas in (2), but did not stress that the fact that $\exp(-e/T)$ combines bias removal with a global parameter because it exists in a scenario where there is a distributed quantity, total energy.

$\exp(ipx)$ only exhibits bias removal, i.e. local conservation of momentum, because it does not live in a global world of a distributed quantity. One must freeze out motion $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ to move to

the global world of a distributed quantity, i.e. $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$.

Single Particle Quantum Bound State and Entropy Considerations

A Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution exists in a global situation with a distributed quantity, namely total energy. As a result, one may remove bias either globally or locally. If one removes it locally, then one uses:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4) \text{ if } e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4 \quad ((6))$$

$P(e_1)$, however, is the probability to find an e_1 in the global scenario and so should contain a parameter related to the global energy, i.e.

$$P(e_1) \text{ is really } P(e_1, E) = C \exp(-e/T) \text{ where } T \text{ is linked with global energy } ((7))$$

An alternative way to remove bias is to directly consider the distribution of energy and maximize the \ln of the number of ways to distribute subject to a constraint one average energy. Using \ln breaks a product into sums:

$$\text{Extremize } \ln(N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!) + 1/T \text{ Sum over } i e_i n(e_i) \quad ((8))$$

This also leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor.

In the quantum case, two particles scatter and momentum is conserved. As a result, even in the case of a potential $V(x)$ and conserved energy, the picture is one of impulse hits and conservation of momentum. $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ represents the distributed world and $\exp(ipx)$ the local world of impulse hits. As a result, $V(x)$, the potential, represents average energy at each x , but really impulse hits are delivered. Given that the $\exp(ipx)$ level is local and does not deal with a distributed quantity, one sees that there is no maximization of entropy a second time to find weights of:

$$W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

This is not an accident. The motion freeze out used to obtain $\exp(ipx)$ automatically leads to orthogonal functions. Local impulse hits exist in the local world of momentum conservation, i.e. ((9)) and not at the level of $W^*(x)W(x)$, i.e. the distributed world. As a result, it may seem that one distributes the total bound energy, but the impulse picture does not deal with distribution and orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$ s ensures that energy conservation yields a unique value for $a(p)$ s for an E_n we think. Using average conservation of energy yields:

$$(\text{Sum over } p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)) / (\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((10))$$

One must also insist on $W(x)$ dropping at the classical turning points which is a boundary condition. Converting to a differential equation,

$$-1/2m d/dx d/dx W + V(x)W = E_n W \quad ((11))$$

one sees that there are unique solutions for discrete E_n for the boundary condition. These correspond to unique sets of $a_n(p)$. The W_n are orthonormal, just as $\exp(ipx)$ s are. One does not need an extremization of entropy to find $a(p)$ values, as each W_n has a unique set of $a(p)$ s. These are based on making $W_n(x)$ s orthogonal, not on removing all bias as in maximization of entropy.

One may note that ((11)) exists strictly in the world of the wavefunction, i.e. the world without a

distributed quantity, even though E_n and even $V(x)$ appear as if they could be distributed. This does not mean that a distributed world does not exist. $W^*(x)W(x)$ is a spatial probability in a distributed picture, but it follows from $W(x)$ which in turn comes from ((11)). Furthermore, $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ is also associated with a distributed picture. It shows how E_n is distributed among momenta (i.e. possible kinetic energies) with x points being unknown.

Thus in quantum mechanics, a distributed world exists, it is just not the one that is used to solve the problem. It is the wavefunction world, linked with impulse hits, local conservation of momentum and orthogonality which governs the problem, we argue, and not maximization of entropy, i.e. removal of all bias.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that extremization of Shannon's entropy is used to remove bias and so may be associated with a local conservation law. In the case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, this is conservation of energy, while in the case of $\exp(ipx)$, it is conservation of momentum. We argue, however, that there is another feature which exists, namely that of global distributed quantity. For a MB gas, total energy is such a quantity. It may be distributed so as to maximize the number of distributions, hence removing bias. In this picture, one does not see the conservation law explicitly.

Quantum mechanics is unusual in that the distributed probability $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ does not coincide with the local conservation picture. Local conservation is one of momentum conservation, but $P(p,x)$ is independent of momentum. Thus, one needs to create a $P_{\text{special}}(x,p)$, which explicitly contains p , and describes impulse hits in space. One may then return to the world of a distributed quantity, x , by freezing out motion, i.e. $P(x,p) = P_{\text{special}}(x,-p)P_{\text{special}}(x,p)$. As a result, interactions are described in the world of impulse hits, not distribution. For a bound case, one does not distribute energy and try to maximize entropy a second time. Rather, one uses an impulse picture based strictly on a wavefunction. We suggest that the orthogonality of the $\exp(ipx)$ s is important and carries over to the orthogonality of $W_n(x)$ s. One is able to find unique $a(p)$ values for $W(x) = \sum$ over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ which is used to compute average kinetic energy. In other words, one wants orthogonal $W_n(x)$'s and so does not remove all bias as in the extremization of entropy.

Thus, extremization of Shannon's entropy exists for both $\exp(-e/T)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, and leads to local conservation equations, but only in the MB case is the local conservation law directly linked with a globally distributed quantity, energy. In the $\exp(ipx)$ case, one only has the p value of the particle, there is no associated overall system total p . As a result, one needs to find a way to compute $a(p)$ values if one has $W(x) = \sum$ over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but conservation of energy with appropriate boundary conditions leads to a unique solutions (and these are orthogonal which seems to be a fundamental property) and so there is no need of a global maximization of entropy to solve the bound problem. In fact, one cannot remove all bias and have orthogonal wavefunctions it seems. The distributed world still exists, but it is the $W^*(x)W(x)$ or $a^*(p)a(p)$ world which is not directly used to solve for $W(x)$, $a(p)$ and E_n .

References

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